

P45. CUBOSOMES AS NANOCARRIERS OF ANTI-LEISHMANIA AGENTS

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Keywords: *Leishmania, nanodelivery systems, cubosomes.*

ABSTRACT

Leishmaniasis, a widespread tropical disease, impacts over 1 billion people annually, leading to 0.7 million new cases and 50,000 deaths. It is caused by a parasitic protozoa transmitted through infected sandfly bites, resulting in various forms of the disease. Visceral leishmaniasis (VL) caused by *Leishmania donovani* and *Leishmania infantum* is particularly severe, with a high fatality rate if left untreated. Current treatment options, primarily chemotherapy, suffer from limitations including toxicity, low efficacy, and emerging drug resistance. We have identified and tested a new class of anti-Leishmania agents, offering promise for a highly potent and non-toxic drug. However, these compounds exhibit low aqueous solubility, hindering *in vivo* testing. To address this issue and improve their pharmacokinetic profile, we propose loading the compounds into nanosystems that improve drug doses and increase their solubility: cubosomes. Cubosomes (Cubs) made of monoolein (GMO) and poloxamer-407 (P407) (1:8) were produced by emulsification and sonication methods. Cubs were characterized in terms of size, surface charge and colloidal stability by methods of Dynamic /Electrophoretic Light Scattering (DLS/ELS) Encapsulation of the anti-leishmania agent was performed by direct mixing and the corresponding encapsulation efficiency (EE) was determined by a validated quantification method. Loaded nanocarriers were characterized by the same techniques used for empty ones and those with the best physical-chemical properties (e.g., highest EE/LC and stability) will proceed to cellular *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. Cubosomes of 225 nm size, PDI 0.2 and negative surface charge (-25 mV) were obtained stable for at least 3 weeks. Passive targeting to macrophages will be assured by negatively charged surface. Maximum EE%=80.31% of anti-leishmania agent corresponded to 10x IC₅₀ amastigotes and an increase in drug solubility was also obtained.